

Factors Affecting the Utilization of E-Resources Among Undergraduate Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State

Isma'ila Isa Zuru,
Kebbi state Polytechnic Dakingari
Shehu Ibrahim Abdullahi Kebbi state Polytechnic Dakingari

Abstract:- An electronic resource is a modern way of accessing information resources through the use of computers and technological networks. The researchers investigate the factors affecting the utilization of electronic resources among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Kebbi state. Three research question was designed which are what are the factors affecting the utilization of electronic resource among undergraduate students in Kebbi state, what are the utilization of electronic resources among the undergraduate student in Kebbi state tertiary institution, and suggested measures that will help in solving the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate student of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state. Although tertiary institutions in Kebbi state have not fully automated their resources and services, they are rather acquiring electronic resources to complement the paper-based resources because of their numerous important and some of the electronic resources are e-books, e-journals, online databases, and online public access catalogs. Some of the e-Resources software used is Koha Application and Dspace application for libraries. The result indicates that the undergraduate students in Kebbi state tertiary institutions do not fully utilize electronic resources because of the following reasons: Lack of proper network to access information online, and insufficient numbers of computers in the library. A research questionnaire was designed and distributed physically out of 260 questionnaires, of which 249 were dully filled and returned successfully, 5 Likert scales were always used to analyze the data using SPSS version 2.0. With a mean score. Also, the factors affecting the utilization of electronic resources among undergraduate Students in tertiary institutions in Kebbi state necessitate the need for similar research to be conducted to understand more on the topic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic resources have become the most commonly used library materials in the 21st century, with the advantage of information and communication technology. Institutional libraries in Kebbi state Nigeria have long adopted electronic resources with the few available computer systems for undergraduate students to make use of them for their research work. Some of the electronic been utilized are E-books, E-journal for research purposes, e-

thesis, etc. Information and communication technology has tremendously changed the way of utilizing libraries in Nigeria. This help in making research work easy and faster, it can accommodate millions of library database in single folders in a network service and can be distributed with a second among millions of researchers from different countries. Owolabi, Idowu, *et. al.*(2016) in a study on the utilization of e-resources by a group of students of the university of Ibadan, it was reported that e-resources like e-journals, e-mail services, internet, e-databases, and cybercafé were available for the use of students in the university and those resources were regularly used but them to support their research online application/registration, communication with friends and colleagues, complete assignments, academic course works, sourcing for materials for project writing and another personal purpose. Gakibayo, ikoja-odongo, and constant (2013) examined students' utilization of electronic information resources at Mbarara university library, Uganda. The study found that the use of electronic resources was constrained by a lack of computer and information literacy skills, an inadequate number of computers, and slow internet connectivity. The application of computers in information Processing has brought several products and services to the users and that made libraries more competitive to meet the complex and ever-changing needs of the user community most effectively and economically. Universities are the highest learning centers and intellectual hubs of every nation and university library are the driving force behind all the intellectual activities of universities. Universities and libraries are today moving towards having access to more and more E- resources in their collection as they form major intellectual research output of the world.

A. Problem Statement

The researcher tries to investigate the factors affecting the utilization of electronic resources in Kebbi state tertiary institutions. In some state institutions utilization of e-resources is still in the low stage. So therefore the researcher is trying to find out the major problems affecting the under-utilization of electronic resources by undergraduate students in the kebbi state tertiary institution. Salam *et. al.* 2013. More so, because a positive attitude towards the use of these resources could influence effective utilization, one of them is compelled to ask such questions: Could this be a resultant effect of the attitude of the students towards the use of these e-resources?

II. RESEARCH QUESTION

- A. *What are the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in the kebbi state?*
- B. *How often has the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in the kebbi state, is been used?*
- C. *Suggest measures that will help in solving the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in the kebbi state.*

➤ *Factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state*

Tella, Any, Memudu, & Olaniyi (2017) among others have indicated that most undergraduate students have difficulties in using e-resources in Nigerian university libraries due to several factors among which is a lack of information retrieval skills.

Copyright law is another major challenge affecting the utilization of e-resources, as most libraries cannot protect the intellectual property of a given author's work. Because most of the work of an author can be edited and used without the knowledge of the author that produces the main work. Oyedapo and Ojo (2013) carried out a study on the use of electronic resources at Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria, and the under-utilization of electronic resources was observed. The factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students in kebbi state tertiary institutions because of poor awareness, lack of quality internet facilities, and an insufficient number of computer systems in the library.

➤ *The utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in the kebbi state is been used.*

Tahir, Mahmood, et al.(2011) noted that the academic environment has been transformed with the help of Digital technology, which has changed the teaching style and research methods of academics. Today, university libraries provide different online services, which include and are not limited to access to online databases consisting of electronic resources such as e-books, e-journals, e-theses, and dissertations, to help users across the globe., Electronic resources have made things easy for undergraduate students whereby information can be retrieved within some seconds by using the internet as a global connection for researchers and students, so students make use of the e-resources as it makes things easier and user-friendly whenever they are making research online.

Likewise, Deng H. (2010) noted that the usage of electronic resources was not uncommon in a university environment because of the rapid advance of ICTs. The research showed that the usage of e-resources was much dependent on the user and the purposes of using these resources. The researcher identified the quality of the available electronic resources as an important factor that

will lead to the effective, efficient use of electronic resources. The usage of electronic resources among undergraduate students will assist university libraries to better understand the perception and experience of users in using these resources, leading to more effective and efficient use of electronic resources.

Israel and Edesire (2014) state that, changes that have occurred in the world of ICT are what have shifted the content of libraries' resources from print to online information resources. Although tertiary institutions in the kebbi state have not fully automated their resources and services, they are rather acquiring electronic resources to complement the paper-based resources because of their numerous importance. The usage of electronic resources among undergraduate students will improve tertiary institution libraries in the kebbi state to better understand the perception and experience of users in using these electronic resources, leading to more effective and efficient use of electronic resources.

➤ *The solution to the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in kebbi state.*

Ebenezer Ankrah in 2018 cited, Ani (2013) agrees that the application of information and communication technology in library and information services helps in the provision of timely information in higher learning institutions to promote academic work and increase research productivity. Likewise, e-resources will make it easier for researchers from different locations around the world such as the Internet, CD-ROM databases, and online databases.

Online Public Access Catalogues (OPAC), electronic journals, electronic books, and digitized materials.

Luka, 2015 stresses that the Advancements in technology have enabled new forms of handling information and have created more dynamic and flexible tools for managing and making it accessible than the print formats. This has created a major shift from the traditional setup of the library which focuses on the physical collection of information resources, to a stage where information is predominantly stored in digital formats. This will enable the fast distribution of information resources among undergraduate students in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria at large.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this research is the survey method. A structured questionnaire was designed to test the 3 research questions highlighted in the study. The population of the study was 2,811 comprising of the total number of students in the institutions under review. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling table, the sample size became 260. The data was collected by administering the questionnaire to the targeted respondents face-to-face at their respective institutions by the researchers with the assistance of research assistants who visited the institutions involved. A total 249 questionnaire were returned which

were used for the analysis. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, mean and percentages were used and the data was presented a tabular form

A. Data Analysis

Table1: Factors Affecting the Utilization of E-Resources Among Undergraduate Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State

S/N	Items	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
1	Lack of requisite skill in the use of e-resources online.	38 (15.3%)	72 (28.9%)	61 (24.5%)	78 (31.3%)	2.28
2	The interface to the resources is not user friendly	139 (55.8%)	80 (32.1%)	23 (9.2%)	7 (2.8%)	3.41
3	The constant problem of network connection hinders access	229 (92. %)	17 (6.8%)	3 (1.2%)	0	3.91
4	The complicated logging-in procedure makes access very difficult	38 (15.3%)	72 (28.9%)	61 (24.5%)	78 (31.3%)	2.28
5	The library has limited Computer terminals (Inadequate).	94 (37.8%)	97 (39.0%)	44 (17.7%)	14 (5.6%)	3.09

The data in Table 1: shows that the respondents think that Factors affecting the utilization of e-resources with the highest mean are Lack of requisite skill in the use of e-resources online has a mean score of 2.28, Constant problem of network connection hindering access which also has the mean score of 3.91, The library has limited computer terminals (Inadequate) mean score with the mean scores of 3.09, Complicated logging-in procedure makes access very difficult has 2.28. The library has limited computer terminals (Inadequate), the interface to the resources is not user-friendly and there is a constant problem with network connection.The complicated logging-in procedure makes access very difficult.

Table 2: How often do you use Electronic Resources to Utilized E-Resources Among UnderGraduate Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State is been used.

S/N	Items	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
1	Daily	38 (15.3%)	72 (28.9%)	61 (24.5%)	78 (31.3%)	2.28
2	Weekly	94 (37.8%)	97 (39.0%)	44 (17.7%)	14 (5.6%)	3.09
3	Monthly	38 (15.3%)	72 (28.9%)	61 (24.5%)	78 (31.3%)	2.28
4	Quarterly	139 (55.8%)	80 (32.1%)	23 (9.2%)	7 (2.8%)	3.41
5	Yearly	229 (92.0%)	17 (6.8%)	3 (1.2%)	0	3.91

The data in Table 2: shows that the respondents think that Utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students is Daily with a score mean of 2.28, Weeklywith a mean score of 3.09,Monthly which also has a mean score of 2.28, Quarterly means score with mean score of 3.41and Yearly have the mean score of 3.91.

Table 3: Measures that will help in Solving the Factors Affecting the Utilization of e- Resources Among Under-Graduate Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	Acquiring Electronic Information Resources that have a user-friendly interface.	148 59.4%	46 18.5%	38 15.3%	17 6.8%	3.31
2	Upgrading the Internet bandwidth	236 94.8%	12 4.8%	1 0.4%	0	3.94
3	Acquisition of additional numbers of computers.	35 14.1%	64 25.7%	87 34.9%	63 25.3%	2.29
4	Provision of alternate power supply.	29 11.6%	47 18.8%	54 21.7%	119 47.8%	1.94
5	Training the students when there is the acquisition of new software/database.	13 5.2%	26 10.4%	44 17.7%	166 66.7%	1.54

The data in Table 3: the table above shows that the respondents believe that the following measure can help to reduce the factors affecting the Utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students which are Acquiring Electronic Information Resources that have a user-friendly interface with a score mean of 3.31, Upgrading the Internet bandwidth with the mean score of 3.94, Acquisition of additional numbers of computers which also have the mean score of 2.29, Training the students when there is the acquisition of new software/database means score with the mean scores of 1.54.

IV. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Table 1 shows the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state with the highest percentage being: The library has limited computer terminals (Inadequate). The interface to the resources is not user-friendly. The constant problem of network connection hinders access. The complicated logging-in procedure makes access very difficult. The finding in part agrees with Ekenna and Iyabo (2013) who reported that undergraduate students lacked requisite skills for the use of e-resources and hence are not highly utilized. Skills like how to search e-resources online.

Table 2 shows the Utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state is been used. Revealed that the electronic resources highly used by undergraduate students in Kebbi state tertiary institutions were only e-books, e-journals, online databases, and OPAC databases. Table 3 Suggest measures that will help in solving the factors affecting the utilization of e-resources among undergraduate students of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state.

V. CONCLUSION

Electronic resource skills are indispensable for effective use by undergraduates in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria. However, the extent to which undergraduate students in Kebbi state tertiary institutions possessed these skills is inadequate for their e-resources usage. While the poor information retrieval skills of undergraduate students hinder them from accessing quality and scholarly information stored electronically in other to meet up with their academic expectations and life-long learning. While some of the factors affecting the utilization of electronic resources in Kebbi state tertiary institutions as mentioned are not limited to The library having limited computer terminals (Inadequate), the Constant problem of network connection hindering access, and the interface to the resources not being user- friendly.

RECOMMENDATION

- The institution's management should integrate information skills into the course of study so that students will acquire prerequisite skills needed in the 21st-century digital age.
- There should be awareness among undergraduate students on quarterly bases in other to keep them abreast of the latest update on e-resources search engines.
- The management should provide an alternative power supply to supplement the public power supply to enable the students to have access to e-resources in their institutions.
- The librarian should liaise with the institution management to put in place adequate internet connectivity to enhance access to a wide range of e-recourses for the students.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Adeniran, P., (2013) Usage of Electronic Resources by Undergraduates at the Redeemer's University, Nigeria, *International Journal of Library and Information Science* 5(10), 319–324. and *Information Science*, 6(5): 98-107.
- [2]. Ani. L.O. (2013). *Library and Information Sciences text for Africa*. Ibadan: Third World.
- [3]. Bhatt, S. & Rana, M. S. (2011). E-information Usage among Engineering Academics in India with Special Reference to Rajasthan State. *Library Hi Tech*. 29(3), 496-511.
- [4]. Deng, H., 2010, Emerging Patterns and Trends in Utilizing Electronic Resources in a Higher Education Environment, *New Library World* 111(3/4), 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03074801011027600>.
- [5]. Egberongbe, HS. (2011). The Use and Impact of Electronic Resources at the University of Lagos.
- [6]. Ekenna, M & Iyabo, M (2013). Information Retrieval Skills and use of Library Electronic Resources by University Undergraduates in Nigeria Information is knowledge Management (online), 3 (9). <http://www.iiste.org> from: <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu> u/
- [7]. libphilprac. [Accessed on 14-12- 2022].
- [8]. Gakibayo, Anna, J. R. Ikoja-Odongo, & Constant, Okello-Obura. (2013). Electronic Information resources utilization by students in Mbarara University Library.
- [9]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from: <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/869>. [Accessed on 7-12- 2022].
- [10]. Israel, O. & Edesiri, E. (2014). ICT Skills and Internet Usage Among Library and Information Science Students of Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6(5): 98-107.

- [11]. Luka, D. T. (2015). Evaluating the Use and Usefulness of an Academic Digital Library. Andersonian Library, University of Strathclyde: Department of Computer and Information Sciences. (Unpublished Thesis).
- [12]. Millawithanachchi, U.S., 2012, 'Electronic Resources usage by Postgraduates at the University of Colombo: Identifying the critical success factors', *Annals of Library and Information Studies* 59, 53–63.
- [13]. Owolabi, S., Idowu, O.A., Okocha, F., and Ogundare, A.O. (2016). Utilization of Electronic resources by undergraduate students of the university of Ibadan: a case study of social sciences and education. *Journal of education and practice*. 7,(3)
- [14]. Oyedapo, R. O. & Ojo, R. A. (2013). A Survey of the Use of Electronic Resources in Hezekiah Oluwasan Library, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/884>.
- Salam, M.O. Ajiboye, B.A and Bonkolr, O.M. (2013). The use of library electronic information resources by academic staff at federal university of agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun state, Nigeria, *PNLA Quarterly*, 77(2).12-20.
- [15]. Tahir, M., Mahmood, K. and Shafique, F. (2010). Use of electronic information resources and facilities by humanities scholars. *The Electronic Library*, 28(1), 122-136.
- [16]. Tella, A., Anyim, O.A., Memudu, S. A. & Olaniyi, O.T. (2017). Predictors of information retrieval effectiveness among library and information science undergraduates in Kwara State Universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal).
- [17]. Tyagi S, Use and awareness of electronic resources at IIT Roorkee, India: A case study. *JLIS*,2 (1) (2011).